

GELMGOLTS TENGLAMASI UCHUN BIR MASALANING YAGONALIGI

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Annotasiya: Ushbu ishda Gelmgolts tenglamasi uchun masalaning yagonaligi ko'rib chiqilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: Gelmgolts tenglama, ulash sharti, Gauss-Ostrogradskiy formulasi.

Ω_0 sohada quyidagi

$$u_{xx} + u_{yy} - \lambda^2 u = 0 \quad (1)$$

Gelmgolts tenglamasini qaraymiz. Bu yerda Ω_0 -
 $\bar{\sigma} = \{(x, y) : x^2 + y^2 = 1, x \geq 0, y \geq 0\}$ chorak aylana, $\overline{OA} = \{(x, 0) : 0 \leq x \leq 1\}$ va
 $\overline{OB} = \{(0, y) : 0 \leq y \leq 1\}$ kesmalar bilan chegaralangan soha, λ -sonli parametr.

$E^{(3)}$ **masala:** Shunday $u(x, y) \in C^1(\overline{\Omega_0}) \cup C^2(\Omega_0)$ funksiya topilsinki, Ω_0 sohada (1) tenglamani va quyidagi

$$u(x, y) = \varphi(x, y), (x, y) \in \sigma_0, \quad (2)$$

$$u(z, 0) = -u(0, z) + g_1(z), 0 \leq z \leq 1, \quad (3)$$

$$\lim_{y \rightarrow +0} u_y(z, y) = \lim_{x \rightarrow +0} u_x(x, z) + g_2(z), 0 < z < 1, \quad (4)$$

shartlarni qanoatlantirsin, bu yerda $\varphi(x, y)$, $g_1(z)$, $g_2(z)$ - berilgan uzluksiz funksiyalar, $u(z, 0)$, $u(0, z) \in C[0, 1] \cap C^2[0, 1]$, $\lim_{y \rightarrow +0} u_y(z, y)$, $\lim_{x \rightarrow +0} u_x(x, z) \in C^2(0, 1)$ bo'lib, $z \rightarrow 0, z \rightarrow 1$ da 1 dan kichik maxsuslikka ega bo'lishi mumkin;

$$\varphi(1, 0) + \varphi(0, 1) = g_1(1).$$

$u(x, y)$ funksiya $E^{(3)}$ masalaning yechimi bo'lsin. Ushbu belgilashlarni kiritamiz:

$$\tau_1(x) = u(x, 0), 0 \leq x \leq 1; \nu_1(x) = \lim_{y \rightarrow +0} u_y(x, y), 0 < x < 1;$$

$$\tau_2(y) = u(0, y), 0 \leq y \leq 1; \nu_2(y) = \lim_{x \rightarrow +0} u_x(x, y), 0 < y < 1;$$

Teorema. $E^{(3)}$ masalaning yechimi mavjud bo'lsa, u yagonadir.

Isbot. Faraz qilaylik, $E^{(3)}$ masalaning yechimi ikkita bo'lsin. Ularning ayirmasini

$$u(x, y) = u_1(x, y) - u_2(x, y) \quad (5)$$

deb belgilaylik. U holda $E^{(3)}$ masalaga mos quyidagi bir jinsli masalaga ega bo'lamiz:

$$u_{xx} + u_{yy} - \lambda^2 u = 0, \quad (6)$$

$$u(x, y) = 0, \quad (x, y) \in \sigma_0;$$

$$u(z, 0) = -u(0, z), \quad 0 \leq z \leq 1;$$

$$\lim_{y \rightarrow +0} u_y(z, y) = \lim_{x \rightarrow +0} u_x(x, z), \quad 0 < z < 1.$$

Agar biz yangi hosil bo'lgan bu masalaning yechimini $u(x, y) \equiv 0$ ekanligini isbotlay olsak, (5) ga asosan $E^{(3)}$ masalaning yechimini yagonaligini isbotlagan bo'lamiz. Buning uchun (6) tenglamani $u(x, y)$ ga ko'paytirib, so'ngra quyidagi hisoblashlarni bajaramiz:

$$(uu_x)_x = u_x u_x + uu_{xx} = uu_{xx} + u_x^2;$$

$$(uu_y)_y = u_y u_y + uu_{yy} = uu_{yy} + u_y^2;$$

Bulardan kelib chiqadiki,

$$u(u_{xx}^2 + u_{yy}^2 - \lambda^2 u) = (uu_x)_x + (uu_y)_y - [u_x^2 + u_y^2 + \lambda^2 u^2].$$

Oxirgi tenglikni ikkala tomonini Ω_0 soha bo'yicha integrallaymiz va Gauss-Ostrogradskiy formulasini [1] qo'llaymiz:

$$\iint_{\Omega_0} \{(uu_x)_x + (uu_y)_y\} dx dy = \iint_{\Omega_0} [u_x^2 + u_y^2 + \lambda^2 u^2] dx dy.$$

Bu tenglikdan quyidagi ifodani hosil qilamiz:

$$\iint_{\Omega_0} \{(uu_x)_x + (uu_y)_y\} dx dy = \int_{\partial\Omega_0} uu_x dy - uu_y dx = \int_{OAB} u(u_x dy - u_y dx) = \left(\int_{OA} + \int_{AB} + \int_{BO} \right) u(u_x dy - u_y dx)$$

$$, \quad \iint_{\partial\Omega_0} [uu_x dy - uu_y dx] = - \int_0^1 \tau_2(y) v_2(y) dy - \int_0^1 \tau_1(x) v_1(x) dx,$$

$$\iint_{\partial\Omega_0} [uu_x dy - uu_y dx] = - \int_0^1 \tau_2(y) v_2(y) dy + \int_0^1 \tau_2(y) v_2(y) dy.$$

$$\iint_{\partial\Omega_0} [uu_x dy - uu_y dx] = 0 \text{ tenglikdan } \iint_{\Omega_0} \{u_x^2 + u_y^2 + \lambda^2 u^2\} dx dy = 0 \text{ kelib chiqadi.}$$

Oxirgi tenglikdan $u_x(x, y) \equiv 0$, $u_y(x, y) \equiv 0$, $(x, y) \in \Omega_0$, ya'ni $u(x, y) = const$ ekanligi kelib chiqadi.

Demak, $u(x, y) \in C(\overline{\Omega_0})$ bo'lgani uchun $u(x, y) \equiv 0$, $(x, y) \in \overline{\sigma}$. Bu tenglikni e'tiborga olsak, masalaning yechimini Ω_0 sohada $u(x, y) \equiv 0$ ekanligi kelib chiqadi, ya'ni masalaning yechimi mavjud bo'lsa u yagona bo'ladi.

Foydalanilgan adabiyotlar ro'yxati:

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